

Ketones as Corrosion Inhibitors for Aluminium 3S in Hydrochloric Acid

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Diacetone alcohol, acetylacetone, acetone and ethylmethylketone have been investigated as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium 3S in hydrochloric acid solutions. The effect of time, inhibitor concentration hydrochloric acid concentration and temperature has been studied. Polarisation measurements indicate the predominant effect of the inhibitors on the cathode. The behaviour of these inhibitors towards various aluminium alloys has been given.

IN this laboratory aldehydes, ketones, amines, anilines and organic sulfur compounds are being studied as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium alloys. The present paper deals with diacetone alcohol, acetylacetone, acetone and ethylmethylketone as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium-3S in hydrochloric acid solutions. Acetylacetone and ethylmethylketone have previously been investigated as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium -2S¹, 57S², 65S³ in hydrochloric acid, however, it is well known that the behaviour of inhibitors changes with the metal or even with the change in the composition of the alloy.

Aluminium alloy Indal-3S manufactured by Messrs Indian Aluminium Company was selected for the study in view of its wide-spread use. It has been specified as follows by the manufacturing company :

Indal-3S—half hard, manganese—1.25%, Fe—0.35%, Si—0.35%, Mg—0.12%, Cu, Ca, Ti—traces remainder aluminium equivalent to IS : 737/1955-NS3.

The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in our previous publication⁴.

The effect of time on inhibitor efficiency is given in Table 1. The polarisation results in Figure 2, and the values of tafel parameters are given in Table 2.

All these four inhibitors are satisfactory. The general order of efficiency is acetylacetone > diacetone alcohol > ethylmethylketone > acetone. Polarisation measurements indicate that ethylmethylketone, acetylacetone are predominantly cathodic inhibitors whereas diacetone alcohol and acetone appear to be mixed inhibitors. This will be evident from the tafel slopes.

A comparison of the behaviour of these inhibitors towards other aluminium alloys is given in Figure 2. The general order of protection is Al-3S > Al-57S > Al-2S.

The performance of the inhibitors in 1.0 N HCl was also investigated in the temperature range

Fig. 1. Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of aluminium 3S in 1.0N hydrochloric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors.

O—O diacetone alcohol
Δ—Δ acetyl acetone
X—X acetone
□—□ ethylmethylketone

Fig. 2. Comparison of behaviour of inhibitors towards aluminium alloys.

O—O Al-2S; ×—× Al-3S; Δ—Δ Al-57S; □—□ Al-65S

35°–55°. The activation energies of the inhibitors were evaluated from plots of $1/T$ against log corrosion rates according to Arrhenius equation and are as follows: Nil, 29.11, ethylmethylketone, 19.32, diacetone alcohol 21.09, acetyl acetone 28.88, acetone 32.05 K.cal. respectively.

Lower activation energies in the presence of inhibitors indicate that the inhibitors becomes more effective as the temperature rises. Machu⁵ had reported that for powerful inhibitors, the activation energy is lower for inhibited than for uninhibited reaction. This type of behaviour has been explained by Putilova⁶ as due to an increase in surface area of metal covered by inhibitor molecules as the temperature rises.

Lower activation energy in the presence of inhibitors has been explained by Riggs³ in the following way. The corrosion rate of metal, according to Riggs is expressed by the following equation.

$$\frac{-d(Mc)}{dt} = k_1(1-\theta) + k_2\theta$$

where θ is the fraction of the surface covered by the adsorbed inhibitor, k_1 is the rate constant for the uninhibited reaction, k_2 is the rate constant for corrosion of the completely covered surface and M = metal.

Although in many systems k_2 may be so small as to make $k_2\theta$ negligible, it is not likely to be zero. It is easily seen also that as θ becomes quite large (say < 0.99), then very small increase in θ cause the term $k_1(1-\theta)$ to decrease markedly, so that it would take a very large ratio of k_1/k_2 to make the term $k_2\theta$ negligible at high coverages. It is probably safe to assume then, that there are many inhibited systems for which corrosion rates at high

TABLE I. EFFECT OF TIME OF INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY

Inhibitor	Inhibitor concentration in ml/l	10 minutes		30 minutes		60 minutes		120 minutes		180 minutes	
		Loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency								
1.0N Hydrochloric acid											
Nil		31.5	—	198.7	—	614.6	—	1762.0	—	2552.0	—
Diacetone alcohol	43.50	5.9	81.0	27.0	86.4	49.5	91.9	138.7	92.1	279.9	89.0
Acetylacetone	26.10	5.7	81.9	37.0	81.4	107.1	82.6	174.4	90.1	325.4	87.2
Acetone	43.50	8.0	74.7	31.8	84.0	96.8	84.2	663.9	62.5	1152.0	54.9
Ethylmethylketone	43.50	11.9	62.0	38.9	80.4	113.3	81.6	246.6	86.2	428.1	83.2
2.0N Hydrochloric acid											
Nil		73.02	—	704.9	—	2061.0	—	5538.0	—	—	—
Diacetone alcohol	43.50	2.7	96.3	27.3	96.1	67.9	96.7	771.4	86.0	—	—
Acetylacetone	43.50	3.0	95.9	15.1	97.9	37.8	98.0	310.3	94.4	—	—
Acetone	43.50	4.7	88.5	28.5	95.9	147.0	92.9	1244.0	77.5	—	—
Ethylmethylketone	43.50	13.0	82.2	90.8	87.1	195.2	90.5	1317.0	76.2	—	—
3.0N Hydrochloric acid											
Nil		26.8	—	956.1	—	4923.0	—	—	—	—	—
Diacetone alcohol	43.50	5.9	77.8	32.7	96.6	73.5	98.5	—	—	—	—
Acetylacetone	43.50	1.1	95.9	5.1	99.5	30.6	99.4	—	—	—	—
Acetone	43.50	3.0	90.9	32.7	96.6	197.3	96.0	—	—	—	—
Ethylmethylketone	43.50	2.4	90.9	37.6	96.0	257.7	94.8	—	—	—	—
4.0N Hydrochloric acid											
Nil		11.6	—	95.2	—	931.3	—	—	—	—	—
Diacetone alcohol	43.50	1.9	83.7	6.7	92.9	12.7	98.6	—	—	—	—
Acetylacetone	43.50	1.8	79.1	5.9	93.8	10.8	98.8	—	—	—	—
Acetone	43.50	1.7	84.9	10.9	88.7	39.2	95.8	—	—	—	—
Ethylmethylketone	43.50	2.1	81.4	5.1	94.6	44.3	95.2	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2. TAFEL PARAMETERS AND EFFICIENCY OF INHIBITORS

Inhibitor and Inhibitor concentration	Tafel slope b		Energy transfer coefficient Cathodic	Corrosion current amp/cm ²		Inhibitor Efficiency from (5)	Inhibitor Efficiency from (6)	Inhibitor efficiency from loss in weight method
	Anodic (volts)	Cathodic (volts)		from Extrapolation of cathodic Tafel Line	from intersection of cathodic and anodic lines at open circuit potential			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Nil	0.02	0.13	0.47	3.3×10^{-3}	3.570×10^{-3}	—	—	—
Ethylmethyl- ketone (43.50 ml/l)	0.056	0.18	0.34	9.74×10^{-5}	1.940×10^{-4}	97.0	94.5	62-86
Acetylacetone (43.50 ml/l)	0.07	0.41	0.15	7.34×10^{-4}	8.120×10^{-4}	78.8	77.3	81-90
Diacetonealcohol (43.50 ml/l)	0.13	0.16	0.38	8.8×10^{-5}	1.940×10^{-4}	98.2	94.5	81-92
Acetone (43.50 ml/l)	0.15	0.32	0.19	1.3×10^{-4}	2.44×10^{-4}	96.1	93.0	55-84

coverages do not reflect simply the extent of adsorption, but rather a new rate expression i.e. simple $k_2\theta$. In such cases, the term $k_1(1-\theta)$ will be negligibly small and the corrosion mechanism probably involves direct reaction of the species 'metal atom adsorbed inhibitor molecules'. There is thus every reason to expect that activation energy involved in the rate constant $k_2 = (Ae^{-\Delta E_2/RT})$ will be quite different from that involved in the uninhibited rate constant k_1 .

It is therefore, not surprising that the activation energy of inhibitor reaction at high coverages can be either larger or smaller than that of the uninhibited reaction. Thus the decrease in activation energy at higher levels of inhibitor arises from a shift of the net corrosion reaction from that on the uncovered surface to one involving the adsorbed site directly.

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